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TITLE: High Temperature Superconductor limiting filters for improving receiver dynamic range

AUTHORS (FIRST NAME, LAST NAME): Nikhil Joshi², James C. Booth¹, Aaron Hagerstrom¹, Nathan Orloff¹, Christian Long¹, Xifeng Lu¹, Charles Little¹, Jordi Mateu³

PRESENTER: James Booth

INSTITUTIONS (ALL): 1. RF Technology Division, NIST, Boulder, CO, United States.
2. Electrical Engineering Department, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, United States.
3. UPC, Barcelona, Spain.

Abstract Body : High-temperature superconductor (HTS) materials display extremely low loss in the superconducting state at RF and microwave frequencies, and their inherently high quality factors enable filters with simultaneous low loss and very high selectivity to be achieved in very compact form factors. HTS devices have also been developed as fast, passive, auto-limiting elements used to attenuate high power microwave signals with little to no leakage on sub-nanosecond timescales. Combining highly selective, compact filtering with such an auto-limiting response would be valuable in developing entirely passive, non-magnetic frequency selective limiting circuits in order to improve the achievable dynamic range of RF and microwave receivers.

In order to achieve this goal, we have demonstrated fabrication of both high-Q filters and auto-limiting devices using the same commercially-available 500 nm YBCO thin films on 3" diameter sapphire substrates. Co-fabrication of limiters and filters requires optimization of device design and processing, as desired low limiting thresholds are typically achieved using thin, narrow transmission lines, while high-Q filters require thicker films and wider line-widths.

To demonstrate limiting filter performance, we have designed, fabricated, and measured the response of compact HTS limiting filters operating at 3.5 GHz. The filters were designed using a Hilbert curve approach, in order to reduce the area required for operation at 3.5 GHz. The linear filter response displayed a measured 3dB bandwidth of 81 MHz, and center frequency of 3.5576 GHz (2.2% bandwidth). To demonstrate limiter performance, we measured inductively-coupled, 2-pole filter response vs. power using 10 usec. pulsed excitations. These experiments allowed us to observe a power-limiting response in a narrowband filter using commercially-available YBCO thin films, with limiting thresholds of approximately 25 dBm for operation at 70K. Critical filter design parameters include the input/output couplings, which control the filter insertion loss and power coupled into the resonator, and the inter-resonator couplings, which can be exploited to deliver power-dependent response to control the limiting functionality.

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